

Spectro-magnetic Studies on Inner and Their Heteropolynuclear Complexes, including Isomers, with Polydentate Ketoanils

R. K. UPADHYAY*^a, MAYA VERMA^a, MANOJ K. SHARMA^b and MADHU^a

^aChemistry Department, ^bPhysics Department, N. R. E. C. College, Khurja-203 131

Manuscript received 23 November 1994, revised 23 July 1995, accepted 28 July 1995

Ketoanils with profound biochemical properties¹, and uses in analytical² and synthetic heterocyclic³ chemistry exhibit novel ligation properties⁴⁻⁶ in forming complexes of unusual stereochemistry and isomeric composition. A few reports^{5,7} also describe chemistry of their isopolynuclear complexes. Synthesis and structure of inner-complexes involving different tautomers of a ketoanil as polydentate ligand, and of heteropolynuclear complexes obtained by reacting inner-complexes as ligands with trivalent cations like Fe^{III} are reported in the present communication.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry of the complexes (Table 1) are in conformity with elemental analysis. The lower values of conductance of mononuclear complexes (2.5–20.7 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) indicate their nonelectrolytic nature, whereas high values (109–389 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) of polynuclear complexes are attributed⁸ to their 1 : 1 and 1 : 3 electrolytic nature.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES*

Compd./ (Colour, M.p. °C)	λ_M Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	μ_{eff} B. M.	Yield of binary product %
[Co(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄)(H ₂ O) ₂].5H ₂ O (Green brown, 110 ^a)	13.2	4.89	39.2
[Co(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄)(H ₂ O) ₂].5H ₂ O (Brown, >310 ^b)	14.7	4.85	
[Fe ₂ (Co(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄)) ₂ Cl ₆] (Brown, 340 ^{c,e})	–	5.43	10.4
[Fe(Co(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄)) ₃]Cl ₃ (Orange brown, 250 ^{d,e})	420.7	5.15	
[Ni(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄)] (Brown, 260 ^{a,f})	18.6	Dia.	31.8
[Ni(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄)].3H ₂ O (Dark brown, >310 ^b)	18.4	Dia.	
[Fe ₂ (Ni(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄)) ₂ Cl ₆] (Brown, 285 ^{c,e})	–	5.09	7.3
[Fe(Ni(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄)) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl (Brown, 210 ^d)	93.7	5.47	
[Cu(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄)].2H ₂ O (Brown, 240 ^{a,f})	9.1	2.10	59.9
[Cu(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄)].5H ₂ O (Brown, >310 ^b)	7.0	2.14	
[Fe ₂ (Cu(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄)) ₂ Cl ₆] (Brown, >300 ^{c,e})	–	5.47	20.5
[Fe(Cu(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄)) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl (Brown, 200 ^d)	123.6	5.18	

Table-1 (contd.)

[Zn(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄)].H ₂ O (Yellow brown, 200 ^{a,f})	2.8	Dia.	35.7
[Zn(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄)].5H ₂ O (brown, 260 ^{b,f})	2.5	Dia.	
[Co(C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄)(H ₂ O) ₂] (Green brown, 250 ^{a,c})	8.0	4.73	19.2
[Co(C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄)(H ₂ O) ₂] (Brown, 270 ^{b,e})	7.0	4.70	
[Fe ₂ (Co(C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄)) ₂ Cl ₆] (Brown, 300 ^{c,e})	–	5.54	23.8
[Fe(Co(C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄)) ₃]Cl ₃ (Brown, 155 ^d)	302.9	5.39	
[Ni(C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄)] (Dark brown, 220 ^{a,f})	7.1	Dia.	11.8
[Ni(C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄)].6H ₂ O (Brown, >310 ^b)	20.7	Dia.	
[Fe ₂ (Ni(C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄)) ₂ Cl ₆] (Brown, 280 ^{c,e})	–	5.40	34.5
[Fe(Ni(C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄)) ₃]Cl ₃ (Brown, 220 ^d)	385.0	5.13	
[Cu(C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄)].H ₂ O (Brown, 220 ^d)	14.7	2.37	16.7
[Cu(C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄)].3H ₂ O (Dark brown, 298 ^b)	12.9	2.09	
[Fe ₂ (Cu(C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄)) ₂ Cl ₆] (Orange brown, 250 ^{c,e})	–	5.12	34.9
[Fe(Cu(C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄)) ₃]Cl ₃ (Brown, 280 ^{d,e})	432.5	5.19	
[Zn(C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄)].5H ₂ O (Brown, 225 ^{a,f})	8.2	Dia.	26.0
[Zn(C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄)] (Dark brown, 232 ^{b,f})	8.9	Dia.	
[Fe(Zn(C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄)) ₂ Cl ₆] (Brown, 250 ^c)	–	–	10.5
[Fe(Zn(C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄)) ₃]Cl ₃ (Brown, 220 ^d)	402.1	–	

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

^aHigh R_F, ^bLow R_F, ^cDMF-insoluble, ^dDMF-soluble, ^eDecomposed, ^fSwelled.

In the infrared spectra, a strong band at ~1 695 cm⁻¹ of the ligands may be assigned⁹ to the ketonic C=O stretch. In high R_F a-products position of this peak remained undisturbed whereas in low R_F b-products it is completely disappeared and a new peak corresponding to C=O quinonoid stretch appeared at 1 615–1 640 cm⁻¹. This suggests that in a-products ligands coordinate through their phenolic groups in benzenoid structure (I) whereas b-prod-

ucts involve quinoid unit (II) of ligands with enolic groups as coordination sites. The intramolecularly bonded OH phenolic/enolic stretching band of the ligands ($\sim 2630\text{ cm}^{-1}$) disappeared on complexation and a new band appeared at $280\text{--}305\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (M–O) in the complexes, which supports the coordination of phenolic and enolic OH groups of ligands I and II, in a- and b-products respectively. The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ ligand band ($\sim 1648\text{ cm}^{-1}$) shifted to $\sim 1610\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes. The lowering of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ frequency and appearance of a new band at $395\text{--}490\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed¹⁰ to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$, reveal coordination of azomethine groups of the ligands. Thus it may be concluded that the ligands behaved

where R is $\text{CH}_2\text{--CH}_2$ or $\text{CH}_2\text{--CH}_2\text{--CH}_2$

as dibasic tetradentate for the inner complexes. Hence, it may be suggested that the ligands form 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) complexes with all the divalent metal ions through their deprotonated phenolic (I)/enolic (II) oxygens and azomethine nitrogens.

Broad or doublet peak structure of $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ band in the Co^{II} complexes attributed^{4,11} to accidental degeneracy of two M–O stretchings, indicates the presence of coordinated water. One to two bands at $975\text{--}820\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to twisting, rocking and wagging vibrations of HOH and stability of dehydrated ($\sim 90^\circ$) complexes upto 190° confirm the coordination of water. Other hydrated complexes, however, displayed bands in the ranges $3050\text{--}3350$ and $1625\text{--}1640\text{ cm}^{-1}$, attributable^{4,11} to symmetric and anti-symmetric stretching and bending vibrations respectively of their lattice water.

Besides exhibiting characteristic frequencies of ketonic and quinoid C=O, C=N, M–N, M–O etc. groups of inner-complexes, heteropolynuclear complexes display one or

two bands at $317\text{--}380\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region attributed¹¹ to $\nu_{\text{Fe-Cl}}$; broad peak structure which could arise due to mixing of two closely spaced peaks or two clear peaks in c-products could only be accounted for by considering $\nu_{\text{Fe-Cl}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Cl-Fe-Cl}}$ in them, whereas single band in d-products is due to $\nu_{\text{Fe-Cl}}$ only. The shifting of $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ band of inner-complexes to lower wavenumber ($390\text{--}436\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in heteropolynuclear complexes obviously shows formation of M–N–Fe bonds, but this possibility could not exist owing to steric reasons. This lowering, however, may only be attributed to the stretching of chelate rings as a whole through the formation of M–O–Fe bonds displaying their bands at lower frequencies than $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ bands.

Inner-complexes of Co^{II} which display magnetic moments corresponding¹² to spin-free octahedral d^7 -configuration, are simple paramagnetics involving ${}^4T_{1g}$ ground state. The band splitting pattern in their electronic spectra is also consistent with the magnetic data. The frequencies of the ligand field bands occurring at $14493\text{--}15129$ and $20367\text{--}21930\text{ cm}^{-1}$, attributed to ${}^4A_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ and $b^4T_{1g} \leftarrow a^4T_{1g}$ transitions respectively, have been used to calculate ligand field parameters, $10Dq$ ($\sim 7726\text{ cm}^{-1}$), Racah's parameters (B , $\sim 973\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and C , $\sim 3793\text{ cm}^{-1}$), β (~ 0.87) and ligand field stabilisation energy ($\sim 4635\text{ cm}^{-1}$) by using König equations¹³. Two high intensity bands due to metal \leftarrow ligand charge transfer have also been observed at ~ 38673 and $\sim 42864\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The diamagnetism exhibited by the Ni^{II} complexes is indicative¹⁴ of their low-spin square-planar configuration. Electronic spectral bands at ~ 15712 and $\sim 21320\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to ${}^1B_{1g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{2g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$ respectively, confirm¹¹ square-planar stereochemistry. Metal \leftarrow ligand charge transfer bands, however, occur at ~ 39567 and $\sim 44343\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Although magnetic moments of the Cu^{II} complexes (2.09–2.37 B.M.) reveal^{14,15} their square-planar stereochemistry along with small amounts of distorted cubic form, the two bands at $20161\text{--}22727\text{ cm}^{-1}$, characteristic to D_{4h} symmetry, clearly indicate their square-planar geometry. Two or three high intensity bands at $34843\text{--}47393\text{ cm}^{-1}$ could be attributed^{4,11} to metal \leftarrow ligand charge transfer. The Zn^{II} chelates are diamagnetic.

Magnetic moments of heteropolynuclear complexes (5.09–5.54 B.M.), lower than spin-only value of spin-free octahedral stereochemistry, could be attributed¹¹ to the presence of divalent metal ions in the coordination zone of high-spin Fe^{III} ; possibility of low-spin octahedral stereochemistry along with high-spin form also can not ruled out. In the electronic spectra of the mixed metal complexes, the first two bands occurring at $14815\text{--}16667$ and $20833\text{--}22222\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with broad peak structure seem to have arisen of mixing of ${}^4T_{1g}(G) \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}$ and ${}^4T_{2g}(G) \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}$ transitions of spin-free octahedral Fe^{III} with ligand field transition of the corresponding inner-complexes as ligands, whereas other bands of higher frequency at $26316\text{--}27778$, 28010--

28 571, ~30 303, ~35 780, 36 540–37 622 and ~38 520 cm^{-1} attributed¹¹ to ${}^4T_{2g}(D) \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}$, ${}^4E_g(D) \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}$, ${}^4T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}$, ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}$ and ${}^4T_{2g}(F) \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}$ transitions respectively, are the clear evidence in support of octahedral field around spin-free Fe^{III} .

Experimental

Ketoanil ligands were synthesised by stirring a mixture of *o*-hydroxyphenylglyoxal (0.03 mol) and ethylenediamine/propylenediamine (0.015 mol) in ether at room temperature and the resulting solid was washed with ether till free from the reactants, (yields 60.2–72.5%).

Inner and heteropolynuclear complexes: Saturated solutions of the metal chlorides and bis-ketoanils in acetone, alcohol or acetone-alcohol (1 : 1, v/v) were mixed in stoichiometric quantities. Most of the products were precipitated immediately whereas a few ones were obtained on refluxing (2 h) and concentrating their reaction mixtures. The resulting solids after washing with acetone and ether successively were dried in a air-oven ($75 \pm 5^\circ$).

A mixture of equimolar solutions of the inner-complexes (as ligands) and ferric chloride in acetone-alcohol (1 : 2, v/v) was refluxed to prepare the heteropolynuclear complexes. Refluxing time for inner-complexes of ethylene bis-anil was 8–10 h whereas for those involving propylene bis-anil it was 20–30 h. During reflux, darkening of colour of the reaction mixtures and/or appearance of turbidity indicated the formation of heteropolynuclear complexes. Solids obtained by crystallisation of reaction mixtures after concentration on a water-bath, were washed with acetone-alcohol (1 : 2, v/v) and ether successively and dried in a air-oven ($75 \pm 5^\circ$).

Homogeneity test and bulk separation of multinary solids: Homogeneity and/or purity of the products was tested by tlc on starch-bound silica gel layers. All the inner- and heteropolynuclear products indicated to be binary mixtures by tlc test were then resolved in bulk. Binary mixtures of inner-complexes were resolved by column (50 cm \times 2 cm dia) chromatography using DMF as solvent and acetone as developing solvent; slow-moving component was eluted with DMF. Eluates were evaporated on a water-bath to dryness. Binary mixtures of heteropolynuclear complexes, however, were resolved by treating them with DMF and filtering out the sparingly soluble component from the soluble one.

In the synthetic work reagent grade chemicals (B.D.H.) were used as such whereas in chromatography the solvents

were used after distillation.

M.ps. were determined in open glass capillaries and are uncorrected. All the samples were analysed for their elements microanalytically at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Conductance of the complexes in DMF was measured on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge using a dip-type cell. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (DMF) on a Beckmann DU-2 spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurement was done at Roorkee University, using a vibrational magnetometer operated under constant magnetic field of 5.0 kG.

References

1. F. D. POPP and W. KIRSCH, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 3858; I. SLAMI and S. UMAZAWA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1956, **29**, 175; V. KUMARI, Ph.D. Thesis, Meerut University, 1983.
2. R. K. UPADHYAY, M. VERMA and N. AGARWAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 241; R. K. UPADHYAY and A. RANI, *Chromatographia*, 1987, **23**, 86; R. K. UPADHYAY, *Chromatographia*, 1988, **25**, 324.
3. R. K. UPADHYAY, N. AGARWAL and N. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **70**, 537.
4. R. K. UPADHYAY, A. K. BAJPAI and K. RATHORE, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1985, **10**, 24.
5. R. K. UPADHYAY and A. RANI, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1989, **126**, 195.
6. R. K. UPADHYAY, V. SHARMA and V. P. SINGH, *J. Liq. Chromatogr.*, 1982, **5**, 1141.
7. A. RANI, Ph.D. Thesis, Meerut University, 1987; R. K. UPADHYAY, V. P. SINGH and S. C. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 781.
8. S. M. F. REHMAN, J. AHMED and M. M. HAQ, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 3351; B. P. KENNEDY and A. B. P. LEVER, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1972, **50**, 3488.
9. R. K. UPADHYAY, K. RATHORE and A. K. BAJPAI, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1986, **121**, 281.
10. C. N. R. RAO, M. N. GEORGE, J. MAHANTY and P. T. NARASIMHAN, "A Hand Book of Chemistry and Physics", East-West Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 1967.
11. J. LEWIS and R. G. WILKINS, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1964.
12. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Fields", Interscience, New York, 1966; P. K. PANDA and B. K. MAHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 137; N. S. BHAVE and R. B. KHARAT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 871.
13. E. KONIG, *Struct. Bonding*, 1971, **9**.
14. P. W. SELWOOD, "Magnetochemistry", Interscience, New York, 1956.
15. R. P. MISRA, B. K. MAHAPATRA and S. GIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 515; N. SAHA and D. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 13.